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Fejlesztési Alap

BEFEKTETÉS A JÖVŐBE

Hercules Routes

Statistics for 2023

GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364

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1. Abstract

The purpose of this document is to present the statistics for 2023 of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364.

The final result of the development of the Hercules Routes framework is a specific artificial intelligence based on learning algorithms, available as a cloud service through a browser and various applications for companies transporting their employees and for companies contracted to transport their employees. The system, running in the cloud, optimises the resources available (passenger vehicles) to transport workers to and from work in the most efficient way possible (number of people transported, km charge). By choosing the right vehicles and routes, significant cost savings can be achieved on the employer side, on the passenger transport service provider side, and in terms of emissions and noise pollution. Costs can be reduced by choosing the right vehicles for transport and optimising their routes. Transported workers can see up-to-date information on their journeys via a mobile app, and drivers can receive information on the route and the people they are transporting via a driver's mobile or tablet app. All this is combined with a complex in-formatics back-up service that ensures the organisation and punctuality of transport, the information of those involved in the transport of passengers, and the emergency alerts and warnings to be issued in the event of an incident.

For more information, please also read the following document: <https://zenodo.org/records/7490333>

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2. Introduction

Since the emergence of industrial parks in our country, intensive long-distance transport has been developed around industrial parks to cover the needs of commuting to and from work. These long-distance services are, with some exceptions, typically by bus and can cover an area of up to 50-60 km around the industrial estate. Unfortunately, the transport service providers contracting with the factories have no interest in optimising these routes, as they typically contract for fixed-route services, including the distance travelled. Such fixed-route services result in underutilised travel capacity and often half-empty services, imposing unjustified costs on the contracting factories and causing unjustified pollution and noise in the surrounding villages. To make matters worse, the factories located in industrial parks do not group their transport needs together but order them separately from the transport service providers, thus increasing travel costs and burdening the environment.

Focusing on this problem, we aim to implement a service package that optimises long-distance bus services by aggregating the transport needs of industrial parks and then working with contracted transport service providers. Although ready-made software systems for road freight transport have been available for a long time, at the beginning of our work in 2016 there was no solution available on the market for passenger transport, so we decided to develop an R&D-based system of our own design.

From a scientific point of view, the problem is an NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem, a special kind of the famous vehicle routing problem (VRP). Due to the well-known difficulty of the problem, the running time of exact algorithms that give perfect results can take several days or even weeks, and therefore these solutions can only be run on small-scale theoretical problems. In practice, a wide range of approximate algorithms are used instead, such as evolutionary algorithm, particle swarm optimization (PSO), ant colony optimization (ACO), artificial bee colony optimization (ABC), simulated annealing, tabusearch algorithm (TS). Although the runtime of these solutions can be measured in minutes, their major drawback is that the quality of the resulting solution cannot be guaranteed, is not known, and on average they only reach the 95% level (gap = 5%).

The framework we developed is based on artificial intelligence adapted to changing weather and traffic conditions, which is able to predict the average speed of the road sections at any given time, and thus the expected arrival times, from continuously logged GPS data. We formulated the vehicle routing problem as a mixed integer linear programming model to achieve guaranteed quality results. The expected high computational performance was ensured by implementing our own R&D-based heuristics.

Our key requirements for the system were:

- Computational requirements:
 - Complexity: handling up to 500 bus stops and 50 vehicles per industrial park
 - Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap $< 1\%$
 - High performance calculation, i.e. short calculation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
- Infrastructure requirements:
 - AI-based self-learning framework
 - Flexible and scalable framework
 - Immediate and complete data delivery
- Expectations:
 - Expected 20% cost reduction through optimisation
 - Reduction of pollution and noise
 - Punctuality, elimination of connecting flights
 - Reduction in administrative time

The development of the "Hercules Routes" framework has resulted in a specialised artificial intelligence based on learning algorithms, available as a cloud service through a browser and various applications for

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companies that transport their employees and for companies contracted to transport their drivers. The system, running in the cloud, optimises the resources available (buses) to transport workers to and from work in the most efficient way possible (number of people transported, km charge). By choosing the right vehicles and routes, significant cost savings can be achieved on the employer side, on the passenger transport service provider side, and in terms of emissions and noise pollution. Costs can be reduced by choosing the right vehicles for transport and optimising their routes. Transported workers can see up-to-date information on their journeys via a mobile app, and drivers can receive information on the route and the people they are transporting via a driver's mobile or tablet app. All this is combined with a complex in-formatics back-up service that ensures the organisation and punctuality of transport, the information of those involved in the transport of passengers, and the emergency alerts and warnings to be issued in the event of an incident.

The purpose of this document is to present the statistics for 2023 of the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364.

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3. Statistics for the year 2023

In this document, the AI base framework was tested over one year period, i.e. from 01.01.2023 to 31.12.2023, according to the following criteria:

- Computational runtime: we expect the majority of cases to be completed within 90 seconds.
- Computational accuracy: we expect the majority of cases to be above 99% accuracy.
- Optimisation impact: measured in terms of distance travelled, fuel and emissions. The pre-optimisation state is the state before the system is implemented, for which we have estimated data. We expect the savings from optimisation to be around 20%.

These statistics have been tested for 7 live sites (industrial parks), the exact names of the sites cannot be disclosed due to lack of consent from the relevant factories or industrial parks.

3.1. Statistics of industrial park “A”

3-1. figure: Industrial park “A” – accuracy of calculation

3-2. figure: Industrial park "A" – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	328	972 056	404 088	147 729	62 063	391 481	164 467	57,99
7:30	230	163 337	71 207	19 123	9 985	50 677	26 461	47,79
14:00	310	554 116	405 220	84 131	62 256	222 947	164 977	26,00
22:00	304	505 382	361 588	77 400	56 388	205 111	149 427	27,15

3-1. table: Industrial park "A" – datas of CO₂ emission

3-3. figure: Industrial park "A" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

3.2. Statistics of industrial park “B”

3-4. figure: Industrial park “B” – accuracy of calculation

3-5. figure: Industrial park “B” – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	93	44 981	29 886	7 500	5 274	19 874	13 976	29,68
18:00	91	31 670	29 564	5 598	5 236	14 834	13 876	6,46

3-2. table: Industrial park “B” – datas of CO₂ emission

3-6. figure: Industrial park “B” – characteristics of CO₂ emission

3.3. Statistics of industrial park “C”

3-7. figure: Industrial park “C” – accuracy of calculation

3-8. figure: Industrial park "C" – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	342	1 147 476	992 239	162 216	141 762	429 874	375 670	12,61
8:00	238	191 539	158 715	28 114	21 386	74 502	56 673	23,93
16:00	238	191 539	158 443	28 114	21 350	74 502	56 577	24,06
18:00	342	1 130 554	969 525	158 188	139 395	419 199	369 396	11,88

3-3. table: Industrial park "C" – datas of CO₂ emission

3-9. figure: Industrial park "C" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

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3.4. Statistics of industrial park “D”

3-10. figure: Industrial park “D” – accuracy of calculation

3-11. figure: Industrial park “D” – runtime of calculation

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Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	344	721 797	463 101	114 403	70 771	303 168	187 543	38,14
14:00	338	551 297	414 620	85 690	63 162	227 079	167 379	26,29
18:00	343	356 227	284 867	40 885	32 148	108 344	85 193	21,37
22:00	338	524 524	389 506	82 459	59 345	218 516	157 263	28,03

3-4. table: Industrial park "D" – datas of CO₂ emission

3-12. figure: Industrial park "D" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

3.5. Statistics of industrial park "E"

3-13. figure: Industrial park "E" – accuracy of calculation

3-14. figure: Industrial park “E” – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	265	126 373	69 049	14 632	8 140	38 775	21 571	44,37
14:00	251	132 400	70 609	15 466	8 281	40 986	21 943	46,46
22:00	232	112 167	61 641	13 181	7 252	34 929	19 217	44,98

3-5. table: Industrial park “E” – datas of CO₂ emission

3-15. figure: Industrial park “E” – characteristics of CO₂ emission

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3.6. Statistics of industrial park “F”

3-16. figure: Industrial park “F” – accuracy of calculation

3-17. figure: Industrial park “F” – runtime of calculation

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Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	190	150 664	83 693	27 081	15 206	71 765	40 296	43,85
14:00	157	78 602	70 698	14 161	12 835	37 528	34 012	9,37
22:00	157	78 602	70 548	14 161	12 800	37 528	33 921	9,61

3-6. table: Industrial park "F" – datas of CO₂ emission

3-18. figure: Industrial park "F" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

3.7. Statistics of industrial park "G"

3-19. figure: Industrial park "G" – accuracy of calculation

3-20. figure: Industrial park "G" – runtime of calculation

Work shifts	Cases	Total distance (Km)		Total consumption (L)		Total CO2 emission (kg)		
		Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Before opt.	After opt.	Savings (%)
6:00	345	833 550	632 047	116 640	92 727	309 095	245 727	20,50
14:00	344	776 553	613 404	115 573	89 062	306 268	236 013	22,94
18:00	164	244 098	32 738	29 626	3 532	78 509	9 359	88,08
22:00	343	741 481	601 205	111 765	87 330	296 178	231 425	21,86

3-7. table: Industrial park "G" – datas of CO₂ emission

3-21. figure: Industrial park "G" – characteristics of CO₂ emission

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4. Conclusions

In this document, we have reviewed the statistics for 2023 related to the route planning and passenger transport framework system "Hercules Routes", identified as GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-01364.

In developing this framework, the objective was to implement a service package that would optimise long-distance bus services by aggregating the transport needs of industrial parks and then working with contracted transport service providers. By choosing the right vehicles and routes, we hoped to achieve significant cost savings and reduce emissions and noise pollution. In line with this, our key measurable expectations for the system were:

- Guaranteed high calculation accuracy: quality $\geq 99\%$, gap $< 1\%$
- High performance computation, i.e. short computation time: $t \leq 90\text{sec}$
- Expected 20% reduction in cost and environmental impact

These measurable results have been analysed on the basis of statistics from 7 live sites (industrial parks) for the last year, i.e. from 01/01/2023 to 31/12/2023:

- Based on the measured results, we can state that both the accuracy of the calculation results and the calculation time have been met in all cases, and in the case of smaller industrial parks, shorter calculation times and often only 100% quality results were obtained.
- Our expectations for cost reductions were significantly influenced by the followings impacts:
 - Geographic differences: there are differences in the route network of industrial parks due to the natural features of the surroundings of the factories, such as the boundaries of mountains, rivers or the considerable distance from motorways.
 - Changes over time: such as the changes caused by the war in Ukraine, which affected production needs, the number of workers and through them, changes in travel distance.
 - In terms of cost savings per industrial park, we have achieved the expected average savings of 20% in all cases, but for some parks we have exceeded this level by a large margin as a result of mentioned changes.

Overall, our work has been successful and we are confident that the framework will be rolled out to other industrial parks in the hope of a more economical, greener, flexible package of route planning and passenger transport services.

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